

Quasicrystal: A remarkable catalyst for hydrogen production and hydrogen storage

T.P. Yadav¹, M.A. Shaz, N.K. Mukhopadhyay², O.N. Srivastava¹ and P.M. Ajayan³

¹Hydrogen Energy Centre, Department of Physics, Banaras Hindu University,
Varanasi- 221 005, India

²Department of Metallurgical Engineering, Indian Institute of Technology (BHU),
Varanasi, 221 005, India

³Department of Materials Science and NanoEngineering, Rice University,
Houston, Texas- 77005, United States America

*Corresponding Author E-mail: yadavtp@gmail.com

Abstract

The energy demand using more efficient or clean alternative energy sources will not only save the planet from harmful effects caused by pollution but could also reduce disparity and create a more peaceful world. The nanoparticles, nanotubes and 2D materials have been proposed as catalyst for energy generation and storage because of their extraordinary properties and ease of production. In order to achieve this information, we have attempted to create a simple model catalyst of two dimensional layer of nano particles on quasicrystalline surfaces by leaching well defined surfaces of single grain quasicrystals. As the first step of these studies, we present here the effect of leaching treatments on surface morphology and chemical composition of different Al-based quasicrystals studied by scanning electron microscopy (SEM), energy dispersive x-ray (EDX) analysis and x-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS). The high symmetry surfaces of single grain icosahedral (i)-Al-Cu-Fe and decagonal (d-) Al-Ni-Co, (d)Al-Cu-Co quasicrystals and a polygrain (i)-Al-Pd-Re, (i)-Al-Cu-Fe, (i)-Al-Pd-Mn quasicrystal with random surface orientation were leached with NaOH solution at varying times and the resulting surfaces were characterized by scanning electron microscopy, energy dispersive x-ray analysis and x-ray photoelectron spectroscopy. The leaching treatments preferentially remove Al producing nano-particles of the transition metals and their oxides. The leached fivefold surface of i-Al-Cu-Fe exhibits micron sized dodecahedral cavities on which the nano-particles are precipitated. However, no specific microstructure has been observed on the tenfold surface of d-Al-Ni-Co and the polygrain i-Al-Pd-Re. Quasicrystalline surface can be regained after polishing the leached layer, indicating that leaching occurs only in a limited depth from the surface. The use of such 2-D nanomaterials for hydrogen production will be discussed and presented in detail, explaining how their remarkable properties can enhance the efficiency hydrogen production and storage. The 2 hour leached as grown and mechanically activated Al-Cu-Fe layer materials was subjected for catalyst application in hydrogen storage materials for MgH₂. The catalytic effect of leached alloy on the de/rehydrogenation characteristics has been studied. The hydrogenation behaviour including absorption kinetics will be discussed and presented in detail.

Keywords: 2-D nano-materials; quasicrystal; hydrogen production; hydrogen storage.